

Updated Snakemake's Tutorial Material and Documentation

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Updated Snakemake's Tutorial Material and Documentation

1.1 Author

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2 Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

- The introductory tutorial for Snakemake did not work on Apple Silicon architecture because of too tight version constraints. This issue has been fixed.
- The Snakemake tutorial container image used Mamba, which is deprecated. This has been replaced by Conda.
- The current tutorial instructions recommend to install miniforge. As an alternative, Pixi can now be used. This also introduces the use of the [sphinx-tabs](#) plugin in the Snakemake documentation.

2.0.1 References

- [Pull request to fix tutorial requirements on Apple Silicon](#)
- [Pull request to replace use of Mamba by Conda](#)
- [Pull request to add the use of Pixi for the tutorial as alternative to Conda](#)

3 Acknowledgement

*This work was completed during the Snakemake Hackathon I (Geneva, March 10-14, 2025) and supported by NSF awards **OAC-2226378**, **OAC-2226379**, and **OAC-2226380**.*